

Best Practice Document

Best Practice for the Collection, Processing and Storage of Human Samples

Part 4: Collecting Hair Samples

Annex 2.4 to AD4.1

WP 4 – T4.1

Table of contents

1.	Introduction.....	4
2.	Sampling.....	4
2.1.	Samples to be collected.....	4
2.2.	Material needed for hair collection, processing and storage	4
2.2.1.	Hair collection	4
2.2.2.	Processing and storage of hair samples.....	5
2.3.	Collection of hair samples.....	6
2.3.1.	Matrix-specific questionnaire accompanying the sampling of hair	6
2.3.2.	How to collect hair – an instruction.....	6
3.	Sample processing and storage.....	10
3.1.	Hair sample processing.....	10
3.1.1.	Immobilized samples	11
3.1.2.	Non immobilized samples.....	12
3.2.	Hair sample storage	12
4.	Transport of samples to laboratories.....	12
5.	Tailored sampling protocol	14

Authors and Acknowledgements

Lead authors

The development of this Best Practice - Part 4 was coordinated and written by Dominik Lermen and Martina Bartel-Steinbach from the Fraunhofer (IBMT, Germany). The document is based on the [Standard Operating Procedure \(SOP\) on Obtaining Human Samples](#) developed in the framework of the Human Biomonitoring Initiative (HBM4EU, grant agreement No 733032) by PhD. Marta Esteban López and Prof. Argelia Castaño from the Instituto de Salud Carlos III (ISCIII).

Contributions for this revision of the HBM4EU SOP on Obtaining Human Samples for PARC WP4 General Survey were received from:

Anna Laura Iamiceli (ISS, Italy), Christina Hartmann (EAA, Austria), Alba Jimeno-Romero (UPV/ EHU, Spain), Marta Esteban López (ISCIII, Spain), Janja Snoj Tratnik (JSI, Slovenia), Darja Mazej (JSI, Slovenia), Zanna Martinsone (RSU, Latvia), Svetlana Lakisa (RSU, Latvia), Andrea Krsková (SZU-CZ, Czech Republic), Vladimíra Puklová (SZU-CZ, Czech Republic), Rosa Lange (UBA, Germany), María Torres Toda (LNS, Luxembourg), Margaux Riou, (SpF, France), Léa Lefebvre (SpF, France).

Acronyms

HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Human Biomonitoring Initiative
ID	Identifier
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
PARC	European Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals
PP	Polypropylene
QA	Quality Assurance
QC	Quality Control
SOP	Standard Operating Procedure
WHO	World Health Organization

1. Introduction

This part of the “Best Practice for the Collection, Processing and Storage of Human Samples” provides detailed instructions for the collection of hair samples to be used in PARC. Please read carefully “PART 1 – General instructions” of this SOP before starting the collection of human samples – especially the following chapters:

- Precautions in the pre-analytical phase (PART 1 – General Instructions)
- Preparations for sampling (PART 1 – General Instructions)
- Sample conservation, storage & shipment (PART 1 – General Instructions)

2. Sampling

Collection and processing of the hair samples according to the PARC specifications is a very important step. If samples are not correctly collected and processed, the analytical results may not be precise or valid. According to the [PARC General Survey Design](#) (WP4, Task 4.1, Activity 4.1.1, Subactivity, 4.1.1.2 PARC Aligned Studies), hair samples from following age groups are expected* to be collected in each study:

Target Group	Biological Material	Sample type to be collected
Children 6 -11 years	Hair	depending on hair length

Hair samples should be collected from each child.

2.1. Samples to be collected

Best Practice:

The amount of hair to be collected will depend on different aspects among them number of target chemicals, the number of analyses or the LOQ of the analytical method employed. Hence, the following information should be clearly defined in a study protocol (see [PARC General Survey Design](#)):

- needed amount

Based to the most recent status of the discussion the following biomarkers will be analysed in hair samples:

- Mercury (Total Hg)

Table 1: Overview – Aliquots to be collected

Age group	Sample Type	Number of Aliquots	Amount per Sample
Children	Hair	1	t.b.d. by laboratory

2.2. Material needed for hair collection, processing and storage

2.2.1. Hair collection

Human hair is a non-invasive matrix that is easy to collect following a simple process that requires only minimal training and no special materials for sampling (Table 2).

Table 2: Material for hair sampling

Material	Reason	Other options
Ethanol 70% & cotton	Hygienic precautions	-

Latex gloves (powder free)	Hygienic precautions	Similar single-use powder free disposable gloves made of other materials
Scissors	Different models can be used to cut the sample, but it is advisable to use scissors specially designed for hair cutting. As the lock should be cut very close to the scalp, scissors with blunt ends to avoid damage are useful	Any clean and sharp scissors of an appropriate size
ID Labels	Samples must be unequivocally identified Labels that contain at least the following information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • identification number (Participant-ID) • date of sampling • time of sampling 	Use a permanent marker pen to write the ID code directly on the paper envelope
Permanent marker pen	To indicate the extreme closest to the scalp Common pens do not write well on the adhesive tape	Any other writing material which ensures that the mark will remain clearly legible
Adhesive tape	To immobilize the lock	Any other material which ensures that the lock remains immobilized
Paper bags	The primary sample container. Paper materials reduce problems resulting from static electricity. The size should be in accordance with the sample (e.g. 8x14 cm; 12x20 cm)	Paper envelopes
Zip-lock plastic bags	This second container protects the sample from liquids. The size should be in accordance with the sample (e.g., 8x14 cm; 12x20 cm)	Any other type of plastic bag that ensures the sample remains isolated

2.2.2. Processing and storage of hair samples

Samples should be prepared for analysis and storage in tightly closed polypropylene (PP) containers in order to avoid deterioration of the target analyte and matrix. Compared to the cryovials for storage of the urine, whole blood, and plasma samples, cleaning of PP containers prior to use is not required since the PARC general survey design aims only at the analysis of total Hg in hair samples. Hence, contamination with this substance can be excluded. Table 3 lists the material to be used in this phase.

Table 3: Material for hair sample preparation

Material	Reason	Other options
Ethanol 70% & cotton	For cleaning the tweezers and scissors between sample processing	-
Latex gloves (powder free)	Hygienic precaution	Similar single-use powder free disposable gloves made of other materials
Graph paper	The segment of sample for the analysis has to be cut from the rest of the strand ¹	Ruler
Laboratory tweezers	For sample manipulation	Any other item that allows correct sample manipulation.
Scissors	The segment of hair sample to be analysed has to be cut into small pieces ²	-
Paper pin	To immobilize the strand	Any other object that ensures correct immobilization of the strand

Polypropylene vessel	For storing the hair samples	Any other container that can preserve the sample from moisture (<i>avoid PS</i>)
Labels	Samples must be unequivocally identified	Write the ID code with a permanent marker pen

¹ The segment to be analysed should be defined during the study design and it is related to the window of exposure that will be studied.

² Ideally, an automatic homogeniser is preferred since it is quicker and the sample homogenization is better.

Note: All used material must be precisely labelled throughout sampling and handling stages to ensure adequate sample tracking. Pre-labelling of vessels is recommended.

2.3. Collection of hair samples

Best Practice:

The hair sampling procedure, as well as the preparation method, varies slightly depending on the length and the procedure described covers the different possibilities.

A detailed **sampling protocol** should be used to document the sampling steps. The following table shows an example how such a protocol could be designed.

Table 4: Sampling protocol – Example

Participant	Hair length			Sampling conducted by	Date of Sampling [dd.mm.yyyy]	notes/comments
	>5 cm	3,5 – 5 cm	<3,5 cm			
001	x				-----	
002		x			-----	
003			x		-----	
...					-----	

Note: The quantity of sample collected **depends on the amount required for the chemical analysis**. This will vary depending on the analytical method, the limit of quantification, etc., and must be discussed previously and defined by the laboratory responsible for the analysis.

2.3.1. Matrix-specific questionnaire accompanying the sampling of hair

Hair sampling should be accompanied by the collection of some basic information related to the hair sample and relevant information necessary for data interpretation. For a standardized data recorded, please use the [Annex 4.5 - Hair sampling questionnaire for children](#).

2.3.2. How to collect hair – an instruction

What to do:

Please read carefully these step-by-step instructions before taking the hair sample. If you have any questions, please contact the study team. Contact details are provided at the end of this instruction. Please ensure that all necessary material for sample processing is available (Table 2) and check if all vessels are properly labelled.

Hair longer than 5 cm

1. Grasp the hair from the middle of the back of the head to the top.

2. Take several strands of hair horizontally and roll them up to form a lock.

3. Fasten the lock with adhesive tape at 5–6 cm from the root of the hair.

4. Cut the sample with the scissors as close to the scalp as possible.

5. Seal the end of the adhesive tape and label it with an arrow pointing to the end closest to the root.

Note: the minimum distance of the adhesive tape from the end closest to the scalp depends on the segment of sample to be analysed (in this case the first 3 cm).

That segment **must be free from adhesive tape**.

6. Place the hair sample in a paper envelope and label it with the sample ID code.

7. Repeat this process with a second lock from the other side of the back of the head

8. Place the paper envelope in the zip-lock plastic bag.

Note: to ensure that the required amount is collected, the locks should have approximately 250 strands. Nevertheless, the weight of the sample can change depending on the sort of hair. The minimum amount required for the analysis must be checked with the laboratory that will analyse the sample.

To watch a training video for sampling hair longer than 5 cm follow this [link](#).

Hair between 3.5 – 5 cm

Hair samples between 3.5 cm and 5 cm should be immobilized ensuring that the adhesive tape is not touching the first three centimeters closest to the scalp. This requirement will change depending on the segment of hair to be analysed.

1. Cut a lock of hair as close to the scalp as possible, following the instructions shown in the case for hair longer than 5 cm.

2. When fixing the lock, be sure that the 3 cm closest to the scalp are available for the analysis. This can be done in different ways. Two examples are describing below.

Option 1	Option 2
<p>Cut a segment of adhesive tape and seal one of the ends. Place the end of the lock in the adhesive tape (be careful to ensure that the 3 cm closest to the scalp are free from adhesive tape).</p>	<p>Hold the end of the lock closest to the root with a binder (bulldog) clip or a staple to a piece of paper.</p>
<p>Place another segment of adhesive tape over the first segment.</p>	
<p>Place the hair sample in a paper envelope and label it with the sample ID code.</p>	
<p>Repeat the process with a second lock from the other side of the back of the head.</p>	
<p>Place the paper envelope in the zip-lock plastic bag</p>	

To watch a training video for sampling hair of 3.5 – 5 cm follow this [link](#).

Hair shorter than 3.5 cm

Note: Hair samples shorter than 3.5 cm should not be immobilized with adhesive tape to ensure that the segment of sample that is going to be analysed is free from adhesive tape.

1. Cut 5–10 strands of hair from different places on the back of the head. Try not to cut large strands so as not to spoil the volunteer's haircut.

2. Place the hair sample directly in a paper envelope.

3. Repeat until the desired amount of sample has been obtained and label the paper envelope with the sample ID code.

4. Place the paper envelope in the zip-lock plastic bag.

5. **Note:** to ensure that the required amount is collected, an example of a scalp hair sample or a picture should be provided.

This is an example of a real sample sufficient for direct analysis of mercury by thermal decomposition amalgamation-AAS. Depending on the analytical technique, the minimum amount may vary and therefore this must be checked with the laboratory that will analyse the sample.

To watch a training video for sampling hair shorter than 3.5 cm follow this [link](#).

3. Sample processing and storage

3.1. Hair sample processing

Best Practice:

Sample processing should be documented in a **processing protocol**. If samples get process immediately after sampling at the same site, sampling and processing protocols can be combined. The following table shows an example how such a protocol could be designed.

Table 5: Processing protocol – Example

Participant	Processed	Processed by	Date [dd.mm.yyyy]	notes/comments
001	x		---'---'---	
002			---'---'---	Sample contaminated with adhesive tape. Sample discarded.
003	x		---'---'---	Not sufficient amount for analysis
...			---'---'---	

3.1.1. Immobilized samples

Remove the lock of hair from the bag/envelope in which the sample is provided using tweezers.

Place the strand on the work surface covered with a sheet of graph paper and immobilize it with the pin clip at the opposite end closest scalp. The graph paper should be changed between samples.

Cut the first 3 cm (or the defined length for the analysis) closet to the scalp with the help of the laboratory tweezers.

4. Place the segment into the vessel labelled with the sample ID code. The remaining hair should be disposed of as conventional waste.

5. Chop the sample into the smallest possible pieces with the scissors.

Note: Ideally, an automatic homogeniser is preferred since it is quicker and improve the homogenisation of the sample.

6. Ensure that the final sample is homogeneous.

7. Clean tweezers and scissors with 70% ethanol between samples and follow the same procedure for the other strand.

3.1.2. Non immobilized samples

1. Place the hair sample directly in the vessel using tweezers.
2. Chop the sample into the smallest possible pieces with the scissors. Ensure that the final sample is homogeneous and label it with the ID code of the sample.
3. Clean tweezers and scissors with 70% ethanol between samples.

3.2. Hair sample storage

Best practice:

Hair samples do not need special storage conditions; they can be stored at room temperature but must be kept away from moisture, for example in a drawer or a box.

4. Transport of samples to laboratories

A shipping date should be arranged between the sample collector and the laboratories for the planned analyses. When arrangements have been finalized, the addressees should be informed of the time and means of transportation.

All information related to a proper transport of the samples in human biomonitoring studies is given in the [HBM4EU SOP "Strategy and SOPs for human sample exchange, including ethical demands"](#). This includes:

- Shipping Category B Biological Substances
- Pro-Forma Invoice
- Sample Transfer Protocol (Manifest)

- Data Transfer Template
- Material and Data Transfer Agreement

Documents can be downloaded from the [HBM4EU document library](#)

5. Tailored sampling protocol

Hair longer than 5cm

Sample **2 locks**, one on each side of the head and approximately at the height of the ears. This allows you to cut thinner locks so that they are less noticeable while having enough amount for analysis. Please note that both locks are necessary.

Grasp the hair from the middle of the back of the head to the top and take several strands of hair **horizontally** and roll them up to form a lock. Fasten the lock with adhesive tape at 5–6 cm from the root of the hair.

Cut the sample with the scissors as close to the scalp as possible and then, seal the end of the adhesive tape and label it with an arrow pointing to the end closest to the root. Place the hair sample in a ziplock bag or paper envelope and label it with the sample ID code.

USEFUL TIPS

Prepare in advance all the sampling material and have it close by. If you take the lock horizontally the cut will not be noticeable. You can use a hair clip to hold the hair.

PARC

Hair length 3.5-5cm

Sample **2 locks**, one on each side of the head and approximately at the height of the ears. This allows you to cut thinner locks so that they are less noticeable while having enough amount for analysis. Please note that both locks are necessary.

Cut a lock of hair as close to the scalp as possible, following the instructions shown for hair longer than 5 cm. When fixing the lock, be sure that the 3 cm closest to the scalp are available for analysis.

Another option is to carefully cut the strand and fix the lock with the tape afterwards ensuring that the 3 cm closest to the scalp are available for analysis.

USEFUL TIPS

Prepare in advance all the sampling material and have it close by. If you take the lock horizontally the cut will not be noticeable. You can use a hair clip to hold the hair.

PARC

Hair shorter than 5cm

Cut 5–10 strands of hair from different places on the back of the head

DO NOT USE ADHESIVE TAPE!

Cut small sections from different points at the back of the head and place them directly into the vessel or paper envelop. Repeat with several sections until you have the desired amount (see example).

USEFUL TIPS

Prepare in advance all the sampling material and have it close by. If you take small sections the cut will be hardly noticeable.

PARC

Sample amount cut

PARC

Examples of sample amounts for the analysis in DMA

PARC

Incorrect sampling

PARC

Correct sampling

PARC

References

[1] WHO, *Assessment of prenatal exposure to mercury: standard operating procedures*. 2018, WHO TEAM Chemical Safety and Health Unit, 151 p, ISBN: 978-92-4-000284-5, WHO reference number: WHO/EURO:2018-430-40165-53693, <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240002845>